

STEAMCRAFT

Second Result Evaluation Report

14. October 2024.

Report

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Project Name	STEM oriented education in the virtual world with customised Minecraft modifications, STEAMCRAFT
Project Code	2023-1-HU01-KA220-SCH-000166153
Action Type, Programme:	KA220-SCH - Cooperation partnerships in school education, Erasmus+
Agency	HU01 – Tempus Public Foundation

Introduction

The STEAMCRAFT Erasmus+ project is focused on integrating experience-oriented pedagogy, game-based learning, and sustainable energy education using Minecraft as a central tool. This report summarizes the key activities, outcomes, and next steps from the flash reports over July, August, and September. The main work packages (WPs) include project management, literature review and curriculum comparison, framework development, lesson plan development, and dissemination activities.

Summary of Key Activities and Outcomes

WP1: Project Management

July:

- Held the monthly meeting on July 16, 2024, where Work Package Leaders (WPLs) provided updates on their tasks.
- Created and uploaded the First Result Evaluation Report, summarizing the progress from M1 to M3.

August:

- Conducted the monthly meeting on August 16, 2024, with brief updates from WPLs.
- Steady progress continued, with the GANTT chart updated as needed.

September:

- Monthly meeting held on September 23, 2024, with WPL updates.
- Key focus: Preparation of the Progress Report for the consortium, with materials uploaded to the FTP.

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Key Outcomes:

- Progress remains aligned with the updated GANTT chart. Next steps include finalizing the M4-6 flash report and publishing key results on the website.
- Across the three months, the project maintained consistent progress, with regular updates to the GANTT chart and continuous monitoring of tasks. No delays or risks were reported.

WP2: Literature Review and Curriculum Comparison

July:

- Partners completed initial tasks related to the literature review and curriculum comparison. These tasks laid the foundation for further work in WP2.
- Templates in research article format were created to support the synthesis of information from both the literature review and curriculum comparison.
- A new folder structure was implemented to facilitate better task management for WP2.

August:

- The initial data collected for both the curriculum comparison and literature review was synthesized into single files.
- Some challenges in comparability were noted due to differences in curricula across countries.
- A wide lens was applied to the project topic, integrating game-based learning, environmental education, and experience-oriented pedagogy.

September:

- The focus of the WP2 tasks shifted toward disseminating the results of the curriculum comparison and literature review in the form of a research article.

- Partners actively worked to enhance the completeness of the data, adding missing information and refining descriptions to make the dataset more comparable.

Key Outcomes:

- Partners successfully identified relevant literature and analyzed curricula across different countries, leading to a better understanding of the project's scope.
- The data collected supported the broader goals of the project, providing a solid foundation for disseminating results in a research context.
- Data visualization techniques were introduced to facilitate discussions and support the presentation of results.
- The aim to publish the results in a research outlet was set, with some potential delays identified due to the timing of relevant submission opportunities.

WP3: Framework Development

July:

- Established foundational frameworks for crafting recipes, ore generation, and custom processes, ensuring seamless integration of these features during the mod development phase.
- Developed a robust system for crafting mechanics, supporting a variety of processes from simple item combinations to complex multi-step tasks.
- Configured dynamic ore generation algorithms for balanced gameplay across different biomes, adding realism and strategic depth to the Minecraft world.
- Made significant progress in preparing graphical assets, ensuring high-quality textures and models that maintain visual consistency within the game.

August:

- Processed all incoming documentation and started developing a concrete implementation plan for the blocks, items, and mechanics required by the project.
- Identified and designed multi-stage crafting recipes and custom processes such as metal forming and energy conversion to create an immersive and educational learning experience within the game.
- Designed the ore generation pattern for specific resources such as lead and silver, ensuring natural integration into the game's mechanics.

September:

- Continued to work on the project's progress report and began implementing planned items, focusing on defining in-game components and assigning their metadata.
- Successfully implemented several in-game items such as the Iron Rod, Coil, Electric Motor, Circuit Board, Lead Ingot, and Copper Plate. Remaining work includes completing the crafting recipes and texture assignments for these items.

Key Outcomes:

- Implemented a comprehensive crafting system that supports various mechanics.
- Developed configurable ore generation for balanced distribution in the game world.
- Developed a concrete plan for ore generation and custom processes, ensuring the mod's educational objectives are met.
- In-game items implemented and ready for further development.
- Work on crafting recipes and textures remains ongoing, but significant progress has been made in developing the core mechanics.

WP4: Lesson Plan Development

July:

- Finalized the Game Design Document (GDD) from JKU, incorporating research on game-based learning (GBL) and energy sustainability concepts.
- Began the lesson plan development, with initial drafts of lessons focusing on critical themes such as waste production and intensive agricultural methods.
- Conducted an internal review of the contents produced, involving curriculum development experts.

August:

- Reviewed the curriculum material developed by JYU as a model, incorporating contemporary educational approaches, such as sustainable energy, gamification, and experience-oriented pedagogy.
- Continued work on the lesson plans (Lessons 4 and 5), aligning them with the STEAMCRAFT curriculum.

- Merged two versions of the GDD from JKU and JYU into a single comprehensive guide for mod development.

September:

- Completed lesson plans up to Lesson 8, covering topics such as CO2, renewable resources, waste separation, fine particles, and deforestation.
- Began organizing the first teacher workshop, setting a tentative date for May 2025.
- Combined best practices and the GDD into a unified guideline for further curriculum development.

Key Outcomes:

- The GDD provided a strong foundation for the design and mechanics of the Minecraft modifications, guiding the development of the mod and curriculum.
- Completed revisions to the lesson plans, ensuring they meet both local and global educational needs.
- Finalized the GDD, including details about object integration into the game, helping guide further development.
- Successfully integrated lessons on essential sustainability topics into the curriculum.
- Progressed towards organizing the first teacher training event.
- Reviewed and finalized the mod development guidelines, completing significant portions of WP4.

WP5: Dissemination and Communication

July:

- Finalized the Dissemination and Communication Plan, which will guide internal and external sharing of project information.
- Reminded all partners during online meetings to share updates, ensuring transparency and alignment across the consortium.
- Continued regular updates through the project's website and social media platforms.

August:

- Focused on increasing visibility and engagement by regularly updating the project website and social media channels with new content, including updates on achievements and work packages.

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September:

- Continued regular updates on the project website and social media, which boosted engagement and attracted new followers.
- Disseminated the project at the Researchers' Night in Hungary, engaging with a diverse audience and showcasing the project through interactive demonstrations.
- Participated in the preparation of the Progress Report, ensuring project achievements are well-documented.

Key Outcomes:

- Increased project visibility and outreach through engaging content on social media and the website.
- Successfully disseminated the project to a broader audience through Researchers' Night, increasing interest and expanding the project's network of stakeholders.
- Maintained consistent engagement through social media and website updates.

Next Steps

- Continue monitoring and updating the Gantt chart.
- Finalize and publish the M4-5-6 flash report and first result report on the website.
- Continued refinement of the Minecraft modifications will ensure that the educational content is fully integrated with the game mechanics, creating an engaging and effective learning environment.

- Further development of lesson plans.
- Ongoing dissemination activities to increase project visibility and stakeholder engagement.

Conclusion

The STEAMCRAFT Erasmus+ project has demonstrated significant progress and achievements over the past three months. The collaborative efforts among partners, effective project management, and strategic dissemination activities have contributed to the successful advancement of the project's goals.